

**EFFECTS OF SUBMICRON GLASS FIBER ADDITION ON
MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF SHORT CARBON FIBER
REINFORCED VINYL ESTER RESIN**Nguyen TT. Nhan^{1*}, K.Obunai¹, K.Okubo¹, Y. Fujita²¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Doshisha University, Kyotanabe-City, Kyoto, Japan,
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yukiko-fujita@ma.dic.co.jp**Keywords:** submicron glass fiber, vinyl ester resin, short carbon fiber, reinforced, modification**ABSTRACT**

The submicron glass fiber (sGF) was added into vinyl ester resin (VE) to modify matrix for short carbon fiber (sCF) composite reinforced at different fiber lengths. The characterizations of fracture toughness and strength were conducted to identify effect of sGF filler and fiber length on mechanical properties of resin and composite. The critical intensity factor (K_{Ic}) of resin improved up to 26% and 61% with the addition of 0.3wt% and 0.6wt% of sGF, respectively. Modifying resin by sGF slightly improved the bending and tensile strength of short fiber composites (1mm). However increasing fiber length from 1mm to 3mm, the bending strength as well as tensile strength significantly enlarged. By contrast, the mechanical properties of long fiber composite (25mm) nearly unchanged with the addition of sGF and was almost the same that of composite reinforced by 3mm carbon fiber (CF) length. The suppression of strain concentration around fiber tip as well as the improvement of fracture toughness of matrix thank to the presence of sGF extended the fatigue life of modified composite for all case of fiber length. At 0.6wt% of sGF, all specimens survived over one million cycles.

1 INTRODUCTION

The incorporation of nano-fillers into polymers has the potential to improve the mechanical strength of composite and change in the electrical conductivity. However, the strong Van der Waals attraction between particles can result in the formation of large aggregates and deteriorate then mechanical properties [1,2]. For particles in the range of 100 to 1000 nm, those can be called sub-micron fillers, there might be an optimal size in between two limits of nano- and micro-scale because this filler balances effects of filled system not only depending on size but also depending on specific surface area of filler [3]. Similar to other thermosetting such as epoxy and un-saturated polyester, vinyl ester resin matrix composite also used extensively in many industrial applications: automotive, electric parts and housings, marine... Nevertheless, mechanical performance of vinyl ester composite is restricted because of either brittleness or notch sensitiveness or both of resin. As a result, improving toughness of resin has been focused for extending application of CRFP vinyl ester matrix [4-7]. Along with the fiber/matrix adhesion, matrix toughness also plays an important role in fatigue damage progression. A.J.Kinloch et al. reported that addition of the polymer-blend modifier initiated plastic deformation of the epoxy matrix phase which was the major source of energy dissipation and toughening [8]. Yongzheng Shao et al. found that modification vinyl ester resin by nano polyvinyl alcohol fiber prepared by electrospinning improved the fracture toughness of resin and the resistance to fatigue damage accumulation of composite resulted in the improvement of fatigue life from 3 to 50 times [9]. Daniel R.Bortz revealed enhancements of 28-111% in mode I fracture toughness and up to 1580% in uniaxial fatigue life of composite through the addition of small amount (<1wt%) of graphene oxide to epoxy resin [10]. In this study, submicron glass fiber with diameter in the range of 0.4 to 2.4 μm and length from 20 to 200 μm used to modify vinyl ester resin followed by preparation of composite material reinforced by chopped carbon fiber. The aim of this paper to report on how effect of submicron glass fiber modification on fracture toughness of resin as well as mechanical properties, especially the fatigue life of composite.

2 MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING

The general vinyl ester resin was supplied by DIC Corporation, Japan reinforced by 12K carbon fiber tow (Toray Industries Inc, Japan) which was chopped into 1,3 and 25mm in length by machine. The tensile strength and modulus of fiber is 4.9 and 230 Gpa, respectively. The submicron glass fiber was supplied by Nippon Muki Co, Ltd, Japan with diameter in the range of 0.4 to 2.4 μ m and length from 20 to 200 μ m.

Eliminating absorbed moisture by heating sGF in 12 hours at 60 $^{\circ}$ C. After that the dried sGF was mixed into VE by the homogenizer at speed of 5000 rpm in 30 minutes followed by adding with hardener and promoter. Degassing the mixture in the vacuum chamber. The type of samples was classified by using the weight ratio of sGF against VE. In this research, 0.0 (unmodified), 0.3, and 0.6 wt% were prepared.

The plate of un-modified and modified-resin was casted in a mold which was created by two glass plates and three rubber bars arranged to form U-shape played role as spacers inserted in the space between two those plates. Resin was gently poured into the open-mouth of that U-shape. To prepare Single Edge Notch Bending (SENB) sample, specimen coupons were cut from resin plate with dimensions of 45x10x5mm³. The pre-crack and natural crack were created by the diamond cutter and fresh razor, respectively.

To observe the strain distribution around the fiber tip of short carbon fiber (sCF), a model specimen of composite was prepared with sCF in 25 mm long embedded into VE. Pre-cracks with crack length approximate 1.5mm was made by the diamond cutter at both sides then natural cracks introduced by slicing razor at the pre-crack root before testing. The sample surface was painted by white and black paints to create a speckle pattern for digital image correlation analyze (Fig.1). Sample size was 40x20x0.5mm³. The tensile load was applied to the model specimen at a constant cross head speed of 1mm/min.

Fig.1 Image of model specimen with speckle pattern from black and white paint for measuring strain distribution (front and back side)

To fabricate composite, the resin was spread uniformly onto a non-stick film followed by sprinkling the sCF on the surface of resin. In this process, to obtain the "maximal contact" of sCF, the position of sprinkle was adjusted. These processes were repeated from layer to layer. After that, using a steel roller to flatten layers followed by putting mixture onto a steel mold and pressed under 15 MPa for 30 minutes at room temperature (RT). The temperature of mold was elevated to 80 $^{\circ}$ C and kept 2 hours for curing the VE. After curing, the mold was gradually cooled to RT, while applied pressure was kept constant. The post-cure process was conducted at 100 $^{\circ}$ C for 3 hours. The samples were cut into coupon type specimen by the diamond cutter. The volume fraction of sCF was 25, 35 and 40% for 1,3 and 25mm composites, respectively.

3. MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS

SENB specimens were tested under three point bending load and the crosshead rate of 10 mm/min as pointed out in the ASTM D5045. The flexural test was conducted following the ASTM D 790-03 at the testing speed of 2mm/min corresponding to the gage length of 80mm. The size of specimen was 100x15x2.5 mm³. The samples for tensile test were prepared following the ASTM D3039/D 3039M

with dimensions of 200x25x2.5mm³. The gage length was 100mm and the speed of testing was control to be 1mm/min. Whereas, cyclic tensile test was conducted on a hydraulic testing machine under load controlled condition. The cyclic sinusoidal load with 5Hz of frequency and stress ratio was 0.1 was applied. In this study, the test was truncated when the cycles exceed the maximum cycles of 10⁶ cycles. The maximum applied stress was set to be 50% of average ultimate tensile strength. The sample size was the same with that of tensile testing.

4. RESULTS AND DICUSSION

4.1 Fracture toughness of resin

The critical stress intensity factor of sGF modified VE of 0.3 and 0.6wt% was improved 26 and 61% compared to that of unmodified VE, as can be seen in Fig.2. The SEM observation revealed that the fractured surface become rougher by adding the sGF, and existence of sGF (inside the black circles at Fig.3b) was clearly observed at fractured surface of modified VE. These results suggest that the fracture toughness of VE was effectively improved by mechanical bridging of added sGF at crack front.

Fig.2 The fracture toughness of resin with respect to sGF content

Fig.3 Fractured surface SEM images of (a) unmodified-resin and (b) 0.6wt% sGF-modified resin after fracture toughness test

4.2 Strain distribution at carbon fiber tip

Fig.4 shows the strain distribution along longitudinal direction of model composites under same level of tensile load. In this figure, the position of embedded carbon fiber bundle was illustrated by black dash lines. Test results showed that the strain around carbon fiber bundle tip and pre crack was increased with increase of applied stress level. However, when matrix was modified with sGF, the strain concentration was suppressed. These results indicate that the existing of added sGF is helpful to avoid stress concentration at carbon fiber tip.

Fig 4. Strain distribution of composite models consisted of single fiber bundle and unmodified/modified VE

4.3 Static strength of composite

Bending strength

For the sake of comparing strength of composites at different fiber lengths, dividing the bending and tensile strengths of composites by the corresponding volume fractions of carbon fiber to get the strength per volume (Vol.) unit. Fig.5 shows the change of flexural strength per CF Vol.unit of un-modified and modified composites with respect to sCF length. It can be seen that sGF modification improved the bending strength of short fiber composites but diminished that of the long fiber (25 mm) compound. Beside, the flexural strength of composites was increased with increase of sCF length as mentioned by Thomas [11] with the outstanding strength improvement from 1mm to 3mm. Using longer fiber (25mm) the increment was trivial. These results suggest that the effect of sGF addition is dependent on the sCF length. Fig.6 also shows the fractured region of 1 and 25 mm composites after test with x and y represent the longitudinal and the thickness direction, respectively. When short carbon fiber was used (1mm), the crack was appeared in thickness direction. On the other hand, when the long carbon fiber was used (25mm), the crack was appeared in longitudinal (inter-laminar) direction. These results point out that the state of crack formation of composites changes by change of sCF length. When short carbon fiber is used, the crack forms and propagates at the tip of sCF. However, when long carbon fiber is used, the crack forms at the tip of sCF, and then propagates along the carbon fiber. Therefore, the inter-laminar like crack formation was appeared in the composites.

Fig. 5 The bending strength per CF volume unit of un-modified and modified-composites with respect to carbon fiber length

Fig.6 Fracture on the edges of composites (a) 1mm unmodified (b) 1mm 0.6% sGF modified (c) 25mm unmodified (d) 25mm 0.6% sGF modified after bending test

Tensile strength

Fig.7 also shows the change of tensile strength of composites with respect to sCF length. Regarding the reinforcement length, the tensile strength of composites was the same tendency with the flexural strength. The tensile strength per CF Vol. unit of 3mm composites even was higher than that of 25mm composites. Comparing the tensile strength from the view point of sGF content, the tensile strength was also slightly improved by sGF addition when carbon fiber length was short (1mm). However, the long carbon fiber (3 and 25 mm) was used, the tensile strength was degraded by adding sGF.

Fig.7 The tensile strength per CF volume unit of un-modified and modified-composites with respect to carbon fiber length

4.4 Fatigue life of composite

Figure 8 shows the mean fatigue life of composites responding to the different lengths of carbon fiber while the number of failure cycles with respect to each fiber length was depicted in Fig.9. For all cases of fiber length, the fatigue life was extended with the addition of sGF. At 0.3 wt% sGF modified composites, the fatigue life improved from 2 to 4 times compared to that of unmodified composites regardless of the fiber length. Especially, at double content of modifier, all specimens survived over one million cycles. These might be the suppression of strain concentration around fiber tip along with the improvement in fracture toughness of modified matrix enlarged fatigue life of modified composites. The SEM photos of fracture surfaces also showed the difference between considered ratios of submicron glass fiber (Fig.10). The fracture morphology of modified composite was more toughness with more debris of resin proves better interaction between matrix and fiber. In contrast, fracture surface of unmodified composite was smooth, failure merely caused by debonding of fiber and resin.

Fig.8 The mean fatigue life of unmodified/modified composites with respect to sCF length

Fig.9 The number of cycles to failure of composite reinforced by (a)1mm, (b) 3mm and (c) 25mm fiber length under cyclic loading

Fig.10 SEM imagines of fracture surface after fatigue test of 25mm composite (a) unmodified and (b) composite modified with 0.6% sGF.

5 CONCLUSION

sGF modification improved the Mode I fracture toughness of VE matrix from 26 to 61% compared to that of unmodified resin. The strain distribution at fiber tips of composite also decreased with the addition of sGF. Static strength tests show that modifying resin by sGF slightly improved mechanical performance of short fiber composites. However increasing fiber length from 1mm to 3mm, the bending strength as well as tensile strength significantly enlarged. By contrast, the mechanical properties of long fiber composite (25mm) nearly unchanged with the addition of sGF and was almost the same that of

composite reinforced by 3mm carbon fiber length. These results suggest that the effect of sGF addition is dependent on the sCF length. The suppression of strain concentration around fiber tip as well as the improvement of fracture toughness thanks to the presence of sGF extended the fatigue life of modified composite for all case of fiber length. At 0.6wt% of sGF, all specimens survived over one million cycles.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Esteban E. Ureña-Benavides, Matthew J. Kayatin and Virginia A. Davis, Dispersion and rheology of multiwalled carbon nanotubes in unsaturated polyester resin, *Macromolecules* 2013, 46, 4, pp.1642-1650 (doi.org/10.1021/ma3017844)
- [2] A. Thabet, Y.A.Mobarak and M.Barky, A review of nano-fillers effects on industrial polymers and their characteristics, *Journal of Engineering Sciences*, 2011, Assiut University, Vol. 39, No 2, pp. 377-403.
- [3] Elodie Bugnicourt, 2005, *Development of sub-micro structured composites based on an epoxy matrix and pyrogenic silica*, Doctoral thesis, National Institute of Applied Sciences (INSA) of Lyon , France.
- [4] Alexander M. Figliolini, Leif A. Carlsson, Mechanical Properties of Carbon Fiber/Vinylester Composites Exposed to Marine Environments, *Polymer Composites* 2014, 35,8 pp. 1559-1569.
- [5] Andreas Kandelbauer, Gianluca Tondi, Oscar C.Zaske and Sidney H.Goodman, *Unsaturated Polyesters and Vinyl Esters*, Handbook of Thermoset Plastics (Third Edition), pp.11-172, William Andrew, 2014.
- [6] K. P. Unnikrishnan, Eby Thomas Thachil, Toughening of epoxy resins, *Designed Monomers and Polymers*, 2006, 9:2, 129-152, (doi:10.1163/156855506776382664).
- [7] Peter Tamas-Benyei, Eniko Bitay, Hajime Kishi, Satoshi Matsuda and Tibor Czigany, Toughening of epoxy resin: The effect of water jet milling on worn tire rubber particles, *Polymers* 2019, 11(3), 529 (doi.org/10.3390/polym11030529).
- [8] A.J.Kinloch, S.H.Lee and A.C.Taylor, Improving the fracture toughness and the cyclic-fatigue resistance of epoxy-polymer blends, *Polymer*, 2014, Volume 55, Issue 24, pp.6325-6334.
- [9] Yongzheng Shao, Kazuya Okubo, Toru Fujii, Ou Shibata and Yukiko Fujita, Effect of physical modification of matrix by nano(polyvinyl alcohol) fibers on fatigue performance of carbon fiber fabric-reinforced vinylester composites, *Journal of Composite Materials* 2016, Vol. 50(29) 4065–4075
- [10] Daniel R. Bortz, Erika Garcia Heras and Ignacio Martin-Gullon, Impressive fatigue life and fracture toughness improvements in graphene oxide/epoxy composites, *Macromolecules*, 2012, 45, pp.238–245 (dx.doi.org/10.1021/ma201563k).
- [11] J. L. Thomason and M. A. Vluc (1996). Influence of fibre length and concentration on the properties of glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene: 1. Tensile and flexural modulus. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. Volume 27, Issue 6, 1996, pp.477-484.